

Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions

Between 2004 and 2018 it decreased on average by 23.10%

Istat-Bes calculates the value of child mortality in Italian regions. Child mortality is defined as number of deaths in the first year of life for 10,000 live births. The data are available between 2004 and 2018.

Ranking of the value of child mortality in the Italian regions in 2018. Basilicata, Calabria, and Sicily are in the first place due to the value of child mortality with a value equal to 4, followed by Campania with a value of 3.8 and by Trentino-Alto Adige and Puglia with a value of 3.3 units. Veneto and Molise close the ranking with a value equal to 2.1, followed by Piedmont with a value equal to 2 and by the Marche with an amount equal to 1.7 units. With an average value on average to 2.8 units for every 10,000-living born.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage variation of childhood mortality between 2004 and 2018. Friuli-Venezia Giulia is in the first place for the value of the growth of child mortality between 2004 and 2018 with a variation equal to an amount of 22.2 % equal to an amount of 0.4 units, followed by Trentino -Alto Adige with a variation of -5.7% equal to an amount of -0.2 units, and from Umbria with a variation equal to a value of -6.1% equal to an amount of -0.2 units. In the middle of the standings there are Sicily with an amount equal to -18.4% equal to an amount of -0.9 units, followed by Lazio equal to a variation of -21.1% equal to a variation of -0.8 Unit and from Veneto with a variation of -22.2% equal to an amount of -0.6 units. Emilia -Romagna close the ranking with an amount equal to -37.8% equal to an amount of -1.4 units, followed by Tuscany with a value equal to -40.5% equal to an amount of -1, 5 units and from Molise with a value equal to -51.2% equal to an amount of -2.2 units.

Italian macro-regions. The value of child mortality has decreased in northern Italy from an amount equal to 2.9 units up to a value of 2.4 units or equal to a variation of -0.5 units equal to a variation of -17.2%. In Central Italy the value of child mortality has decreased from an amount of 3.6 units up to a value of 2.6 units or equal to a variation of -1.00 units equal to a variation of -27.8%. Noon with a variation from an amount of 4.8 units up to a value of 3.7 units or equal to a variation of -1.1 units equal to a variation of -22.9%. Overall, in Italy the value of childhood mortality has decreased from an amount of 3.7 units up to an amount of 2.9 units or equal to an amount of -0.8 units equal to a value of -21.6%.

Clusterization with the K-means algorithm. Below is a clusterization with the K-means algorithm optimized using the silhouette coefficient. Two Clusters are used or:

- *Cluster 1:* Sicily, Calabria, Campania, Puglia, Abruzzo, Basilicata;
- *Cluster 2:* Veneto, Piedmont, Tuscany, Lombardy, Marche; Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Trentino-Alto Adige, Liguria, Umbria, Emilia-Romagna, Sardinia, Valle d'Aosta, Molise and Lazio.

Considering the value of the median of child mortality by cluster value it appears that the value of the 1-C1 cluster has a value equal to 3.9 while the value of the 2-C2 cluster has a value of 2.3. The result

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is therefore the following system of the Clusters or $C1 > C2$. From a strictly geographical point of view, the contrast between north and southern Italy is evident. In northern Italy, infant mortality is about 57.6% lower than childhood mortality in southern Italy.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Below eight different Machine Learning algorithms have been compared for the optimization of the prediction of child mortality in Italian regions. The data were used at 70% for learning activity while the remaining 30% was used for the actual prediction. The algorithms were evaluated on the basis of their ability to maximize the R-Squared, and minimize the following statistical errors or: Mean Absolute Error, Mean Squared Error, Root Mean Squared Error. The following system of algorithms for predictive capacity or:

- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 4;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 8;
- Gradient Boosted Tree with a payoff value of 13;
- Tree regression ensemble with a payoff value of 15;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 21;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 23;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 33.

Therefore by applying the Random Forest Regression algorithm, the following predictions have been obtained or:

- Piedmont with an increased variation from a value equal to 2.00 units up to a value equal to 2.48 units or a variation of 0.48 unit equivalent to a value of 23.95%;
- Valle d'Aosta with an increased variation from an amount of 2.20 units up to a value of 2.71 units or equal to an amount of 0.51 units equal to a value of 23.05%;
- Liguria with an increased variation from an amount of 2.50 units up to a value of 20.85 units or equal to a variation of 0.35 units equal to a value of 13.80%;
- Veneto with an increased variation from an amount of 2.10 units up to a value of 22.61 units or equal to a variation of 0.51 units equal to an amount of 24.24%;
- Emilia Romagna with an increased variation from a value of 2.30 up to a value of 2.59 units or equal to a value of 0.29 units equal to a value of 12.48%;
- Abruzzo with an increased variation from an amount of 3.00 units up to a value of 3.18 units or equal to a value of 0.18 units equal to an amount of 6.13%;

On average, the value of the prediction for the countries considered is predicted growing from an amount of 2.35 units up to a value of 2.74 units or equal to a value of 0.39 unit equivalent to a value of 17.27%

Conclusions. Child mortality decreased in all Italian regions between 2004 and 2018 except for Friuli-Venezia Giulia where there was an increase of 22.2%. On average between 2004 and 2018, the value of childhood mortality decreased from an amount of 2.795 up to a value of 3.6 units or equal to a variation of -0.84 units equal to a value of -23.10%. However, it must be considered that the data may have worsened following the Covid because of the reduction of the ability of the health system to effectively provide even basic health services.

References

Leogrande, Angelo. Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. No. 112860. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2022.

Leogrande, A. (2022). The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Laureti, Lucio, Alberto Costantiello, and Angelo Leogrande. "Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020." *Journal of Environmental Protection* 13, no. 4 (2022): 299-314.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective Well-Being In Italian Regions: A Panel Data Approach. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019 (No. 110814). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A, Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions, 2022, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6590380

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